

REGARDING THE POSSIBILITY OF POETIC EXPRESSION OF PUNCTUATION MARKS

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Annotation: The article cites opinions on the possibilities of poetic expression of punctuation. Punctuation marks “meaning that cannot be expressed by lexical and syntactic means in writing text, expressing ottenks of meaning” needs are introduced as opposed. The meaning that gave rise to the need for the introduction of punctuation marks, especially the meaning ottenkas, make up a large part of the poetic content. Accordingly, the expressive significance of punctuation marks acquires a special essence and significance in artistic speech than in other forms of speech.

Key words: punctuation marks, poetics, syntactic unity, atov sentences, artistic-aesthetic purpose, phonopoetic means, poetic content

But it is observed that today's linguistics sees them more in a sentence as a means of formalizing the mutual grammatical-substantive relations of different syntactic units, and that such a view takes on a stereotypical appearance in many. In reality, however, the verbal form of speech is assigned to intonation to define the status and ensure the connection of syntactic units in a sentence, while punctuation marks are used for the purpose of expressing this tone in writing. On this basis, punctuation marks can be said to “formalize” the status of the syntactic unit in writing. This provides evidence that punctuation is, first of all, a means of expression.

The transformation of the pursuit of perfection in the expression of poetic content into a leading trend in artistic creation led to the fact that from the point of view of formal linguistics, punctuation marks that provide a grammatical-substantive connection of syntactic units began to be widely used to represent the most subtle, yet important points of poetic content. As a result, there began to be a lot of cases when strict rules regarding the use of punctuation softened somewhat in the face of the goal of expressing poetic content, and sometimes the end was denied.

In general, the concept of norm is relative, and its variability is normal. “Written speech at the present stage consists of three units of parts: graphics, orthography, punctuation” . From this conclusion, which was made about the components of written speech in 1974, taking as a basis the darkened separated part, it can be understood that the norm indicated for written speech was different by the time the thought was said, and, moreover, the possibility of further renewal was preserved. Therefore, it is necessary to treat such cases as the result of the need for expression, knowing that it is natural to withdraw from the rules for punctuation in artistic speech.

Deliberate deviation from existing norms (with a specific artistic and aesthetic purpose) means of poetic expression in general (phonopoetic means, word repetition, syntactic methods, etc.) as a condition of occurrence, it makes punctuation a means of expression. The situation that perceived the current norms as strict and perfect, as an addressant deviation

(or error), is the norm for the poet who uses it for the purpose of expression. Because the creator consciously carries out this deviation, what he wanted to say was that the reader imposed the transmission on the punctuation mark in which the Fail was used. In linguistics, "the rules of punctuation are drawn up with the intention of making a tenuous statement of thought, feeling in writing... His (punctuation marks - T.T.) with its application, there is also the opportunity to read the text easily and correctly", the recognition itself allows the creator to freely use punctuation marks.

The reader, who is well aware that the content of a literary work is realized on the basis of various means, also sees this as normal to deviations from a holistic norm. Because at the beginning of the reading, the reader prepares himself to read a work of art and approaches it as an unusual, novel, original phenomenon of Bedouin in all respects. It is natural for a student in such a mood to look for content from any other that is encountered at the time of reading and automatically realize the content that is intended to be expressed through the tools listed above. In particular, expressiveness associated with punctuation can also be included in the order of these. It seems that such poetry requires a certain preparation from the reader reading experience.

"Different characters are used to make a sentence by gathering words and saying them together so that the "mind" is comfortable to understand. All of these are suddenly called "Standing signs" or simplex "standing". "This is one of the most concise and appropriate given definitions for what we call punctuation, from which it is not difficult to understand that punctuation is, above all, a means of expression. The definition consists of two important substantive parts. I.e. (a) to form a sentence by summing up the words together; (b) let the "mind" understand conveniently. The goal of making a sentence is to transmit information ("mind"), but it is not enough just to "collect and Bale words together" to transmit informations. Perhaps it is possible to express an opinion with the content combination of words, but how it is transmitted and "conveniently understood" in written speech largely depends on the intonation organized by means of punctuation marks.

The assessment of punctuation marks as a means of expression points to the fact that its possibilities are extremely wide. The role of these signs in the expression of poetic content is just a glimpse of the wide range of possibilities implied. Its most primary function is to formalize syntactic units in writing and to organize the rhythmic-intonation construction of speech. These two processes follow strictly defined generalizing rules. Such a process can be equally observed in artistic speech, as in other forms of speech.

"Entered the twenty, independence - my son,"

the first comma and dash in this stanza formed a tone representing syntactic units, formalizing their syntactic status in writing. Accordingly, these punctuation marks can be said to be a means of expression, but not directly valuable in the expression of poetic content. That is, these punctuation marks served to distinguish one of the few contents that can be understood from the mutual arrangement of words in a sentence. And the activated content, along with other parts, has acquired artistry. The expressiveness of punctuation marks in this place is indirectly realized. (That is, the punctuation mark itself had its effect on the content, not directly, but through the vasmun it was activating.) Without the above two punctuation marks in mind, the stanza converges on a single cross-sectional form to represent a single thought. That is, the lyrical hero is realized that he is transmitting information to his son about the entry of Independence into the twenty. With the use of punctuation marks as above,

however, the sentence takes the form of two cross-sections, and the fact that the Independence is in the twenty and that he is a child to the lyrical Hero (dear, immature in sight, etc.) is understood. In this place, the expressive function of the punctuation mark was carried out before the transmitted information became an artistic phenomenon.

Any appearance of withdrawal from the existing rules associated with the use of punctuation marks can be called individual norms of the author, the voluntary use of punctuation marks. The syntactic unit serving the expression of poetic content and the purpose of organizing intonation is considered as a means of expressing poetic content in relation to the punctuation marks applied. Russian scholars look at the issue as a separate branch, evaluating it as "poetic punctuation", and pointing out that "it does not conform to grammatical rules at all" from the quality of its most important feature. It should be noted that such use should be assessed as a positive "opportunity" only for the poet and prose writer.

Relying on the above, it would be correct to say that while the punctuation marks encountered in the composition of a work of art are all instruments of expression, not all of them are instruments of poetic expression. Such polefunctionality of punctuation is also evidenced by the explanation of "the cytilistic functions of punctuation and the properties of expressing emotionality".

"Punctuation is the sum of the only laws-rules on the application of punctuation marks" from the reason for the above features when the word goes about artistic speech" views such as lose their value. Relying on the above, it will be correct to evaluate the punctuation marks used in poetic speech as a graphic unit and look at it as a means of poetic expression.

The fact that a punctuation mark is a means of expression or a means of poetic expression is characterized by what purpose it is applied, and not by what punctuation it is or in what position it is applied. Accordingly, two important properties of punctuation marks applied as a means of poetic expression:

- a) the choice of the same one of the alternative punctuation marks as a specific goal;
- a) the choice of the same one for a specific purpose among alternative punctuation marks;
- b) it will be appropriate to emphasize the deliberate application contrary to the current norms.

"Punctuation is the sum of the only laws-rules on the application of punctuation marks" from the reason for the above features when the word goes about artistic speech" views such as lose their value. Relying on the above, it will be correct to evaluate the punctuation marks used in poetic speech as a graphic unit, a means of poetic expression.

The first verse of Chulpan's poem "from the book of nature" is after "the spring" "... the punctuation mark is applied. In this place, the sentence "the spring" is at the same time in full harmony with the syntactic unit that we call the "atov sentence", which embodies a certain landscape in front of a person. Once this part is evaluated as a sentence, a dot, interrogative, plural dot, or exclamation mark must be placed at the end of the sentence. But the poet, after this part, applied one of the alternative punctuation marks, many points, from which, of course, a certain artistic goal was intended. The poet at the same time is in no hurry to express his experiences associated with the "the spring". If the sentence was followed by a dot, exclamation, or interrogative mark, the expression goal of the creator would be activated along with the "the spring", and the content would be judged by the reader as a "the spring" in the creator's position. With this, the reader focuses not all his attention on the bruise, but on the contrary, on the second part, which he describes, comments on. In contrast, the

application of a multiple point constitutes the acquisition of a certain tin between the two parts of the stanza (a process that occurs asocially in the mind of the reader aware of the multiple point's applicability positions). The "readability" (reactivation) of a sentence along with multiple points creates conditions for the revitalization of the "the spring" in the reader's imagination. The poet's vision of forming a "personal the spring" in the eyes of the reader is "... clarifies the reason for the use of the punctuation mark.

It should be noted that in the imagination of the reader, the imagination associated with the revived the spring goes beyond the influence of the creator. In addition to having an individual appearance, everyone's brood also has in many cases common features such as peace, calmness, light, warmth, hope for tomorrow, celebration, rejuvenation. The artistic purpose of the creator is to activate in the imagination of the reader not only the spring, but also the above-listed experiences associated with it. With this, the creator achieves his goal of increasing the level of influence, while providing the reader with a picture of the rainbow in his imagination – a picture of "the peaceful sleep of the Earth is disturbed". When compared, the poet, who aims to transmit negative experiences to the reader, first moves it from a neutral state to a positive one, thereby increasing the power of the "the spring".

In conclusion, intonation has great expressive value in any form of speech. In particular, in artistic speech, especially in a lyrical work, its expressive value increases even more.

The problem of expressing intonation in writing is largely eliminated by the feature of punctuation. In general, it is appropriate to explain the introduction of punctuation marks by the need to express intonation in writing. It is used under strict rules in other forms of speech, unlike artistic speech, and it is fully suitable for the nature of the types of speech provided for.

In the form of artistic speech, punctuation marks, like other means of expression, also acquire an expressive value in a new way, which causes creativity, imagination and experience.

Over time, the introduction of poetic methods of expression into other forms of speech is natural, since humanity always needs expressive perfection.

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